

Options for substitution of gas applications via sector integration technologies

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Key words: <ul style="list-style-type: none">– Substituting natural gas– Natural gas applications– Promising key integration technologies– Modelling substitution pathways	Abstract: Natural Gas can only be a bridge to an emission free energy supply. Until 2050 most processes in the whole economy need to be transformed. For current applications of natural gas two possibilities exist: substitution of natural gas by SNG and biomethane or substitution by using another (sector coupling or integration) technology. In this paper, current gas applications are identified, and integration technologies are presented. Further, transformation pathways for heat supply applications (based on a transformation model applying learn curves to technologies) are presented.
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1 Introduction

To stop climate change, the defossilisation of the global economy until the end of this century is an indispensable development.¹ This reduction is only possible, if conventional fuels are substituted² as an extensive deployment of Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) is unlikely to occur.³ While the end of using coal and oil seem to be within one's reach, natural gas is often promoted as a bridge technology.⁴ Although, it ranks among the lowest CO₂ emitting fossil fuels,⁵ this bridge must not be too long to achieve the climate goals.⁶ As is shown in Kochems et al. (2018), this is reflected by most current energy system analyses. Although they correlate concerning a (strong) decrease in the natural gas consumption, the fields of application for the rest of natural gas differentiate significantly between the studies. Furthermore, it is stated that natural gas cannot completely be replaced by biogas or synthetic natural gas (especially not the entire natural gas consumed by low-pressure consumers today).⁷ Thus, the question raises, where natural gas can be replaced and to which extent. To answer these questions, this paper analyses how natural gas is currently used, and it introduces key substitution technologies. Finally, substitution pathways for the heat sector are analysed more in detail. For this purpose, a meta-analysis to identify the most important substitution technologies is conducted. Based on the results of this analysis, a transformation model with endogenous learning curves is developed and applied to the heat sector.

The bulk of (primary) energy from natural gas is used by final energy consumers in Germany. Thereof about 40 % is consumed each in the industry and the household sector, while the trade and services sector holds responsible for approximately 20 %.⁸ Thus, it seems reasonable to point out technical reduction possibilities for each sector. Nevertheless, many substitution technologies can be applied in several sectors. As natural gas is barely used in the transport sector,⁹ this sector is excluded from further analysis. For reducing natural gas usage, next to efficiency increase, two general substitution options remain. On the one hand, natural gas can be replaced directly by emission free power-to-gas (PtG). On the other hand, a replacement of the applied technology at consumer side is possible.

The analysis is structured as follows. First, principal options of substituting natural gas by power-to-gas (PtG) are summarized.¹⁰ Afterwards, the substitution of natural gas applications is discussed. In this context, chapter 2 gives an overview of recent applications and key substitution technologies in Germany, followed by chapter 3 describing the research method for identifying important key substitution technologies and explaining the model structure. Finally, chapter 4.1 shows the results of the meta-analysis and the modelling results. The analysis ends with a critical evaluation and conclusion. In general, most of the analysed technologies are defined as sector integration technologies. As there exist several definitions, sector integration technologies within this paper are defined as technologies, using far predominantly renewable electricity or other renewable energies as well as renewable raw materials for new, intersectoral applications or intensified usage of known intersectoral applications.¹¹

¹ See Schleussner et al. 2016, p. 2.

² Mattauch 2015.

³ For costs see: Gielen and Taylor 2007, p. 907; for acceptance see: Dütschke et al. 2016.

⁴ For powerplants see: Neslen 2017; Kobus 2017; Bridge technology: Levi 2013

⁵ Quaschnig 2015, p. 48.

⁶ UNFCCC Article 3, Paragraph 1(a) in combination with; Levi 2013.

⁷ More information in Kochems et al. 2018.

⁸ AGEB 2019a.

⁹ AGEB 2019a.

¹⁰ For technological details see: Milanzi et al. 2018b.

¹¹ Wietschel et al. 2018, p. 48, translation by author.

2 Status quo of natural gas usage in Germany and key integration technologies

Natural gas can either be substituted by renewable SNG via PtG or biomethane (summarized in the following as substitution of 1st degree), or by changing the applied technology, thus, replacing natural gas by electricity or biomass (defined as process substitution or substitution of 2nd degree in the following). However, it must be noticed that the amount of biomass is very limited, and its usage should be selected very carefully. In order to assess the substitution possibilities of natural gas, firstly the current use of natural gas must be known and secondly an overview of substitution technologies must be provided. This will be done in the following.

Since the use of natural gas in the consumption sectors 1) households, 2) trade and services, as well as 3) industry is very different, these application cases are presented individually. Due to the limitations on biomass, the focus is on electricity-based technologies. If process substitution is applied, substitution technologies need to deliver useful energy to the end user by definition. However, especially for the industry sector, the differentiation between final and useful energy is not very easy. Hence, where no information about useful energy is found, final energy is used.¹²

For the analysis, the energy use is separated into using light, heat, cold, electricity, or mechanical energy.¹³ Further heat can be differentiated into process heat, warm water and space heating. As there exist different definitions of process heat (or cold), for a clear understanding, a brief definition is given in the following. Process heat (and cold) within this paper is defined “as *heat (or cold) used for manufacturing, processing or refining of products or the provision of a service. This includes services in households and excludes space heating in industries or small and medium sized businesses.*”¹⁴ Cold is separated into process cold or air conditioning respectively.¹⁵ Since warm water is generally provided by the same technologies as either space heat or process heat, warm water is subsumed technology-wise in the following between these two.

2.1 Households

Heat is dominating the energy demand of German households with approximately 90 % of the final energy consumption. Further, natural gas is almost exclusively used for heat production in this sector, being responsible to satisfy around 40 % of the overall head demand.¹⁶ This correspondence to a 43 % share of natural gas usage for space heating and even a share of 50 % for hot water preparation. However, natural gas is nearly insignificant concerning process heat supply in households, as can be seen in Figure 1.¹⁷

There exist attempts of combining natural gas with solar thermal energy or geothermal energy to provide space heating and hot water, especially due to energy efficiency regulations.¹⁸ Thus, a reduction of the natural gas consumption in households as stated by Kochems et al. (2018) seems realistic from a technological perspective. The following gives an overview of current natural gas-based technologies in households as well as principle substitution technologies.

¹² Within this paper, end energy is understood as energy „at the house wall“, while useful energy is the energy utilized by the consumer ultimately, i.e. “beyond the meter”.

¹³ Heinrich 2015, S.31.

¹⁴ Nast et al. 2010, p. 4; Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle 2015, p. 2.

¹⁵ Frondel and Ritter 2011, p. 12.

¹⁶ AGEB 2018, p. 26, other important energy carriers are mineral oil and renewable energies.

¹⁷ AGEB 2018, p. 26.

¹⁸ Vetter 2015.

Figure 1: Total final energy consumption (TFEC) through heat demand in households divided into space heat, hot water and process heat (2009 – 2017)

Source: Data from BMWi, Tab 7b (2019)

2.1.1 Recent Technologies

The next paragraphs give an overview of different technologies currently used in households. The technologies are clustered according to their field of application in this sector. If a technology can be used in different fields, it is presented within the first chronologic order.

Light from natural gas can be produced by lanterns and gas flares. Further, gas is used in several fireplaces. However, the efficiency for lighting is very low, compared to electricity-based lighting technologies. For **space heating** one can distinguish between district resp. local heating, central heating or floor and domestic heating technologies. The first will mainly be done by gas-motors in decentral combined heat and power plants (CHPs) or even by fuel cells. Both can also be used for central heating. Further options for central and domestic heating are (condensing) boilers, furnaces, air heating units or gas radiation heating systems. Applications with heat pumps (gas fired) are also possible as so-called adsorption or absorption heat pumps. Mobile heating devices do exist in form of radiation heating systems and can be used inside as well as outside. All space heating technologies are characterized by a high efficiency and flexibility. The first holds especially for condensing boilers. Next to boilers, especially for hot water production, gas-based flow heaters can be used.

Process heating is needed mainly for cooking. Technologies applied are gas stoves, gas ovens and gas barbeques. All of these have the advantage of producing high temperature heat efficiently and being very flexible concerning the process control. Additionally, there are some rather seldom usages applications such as gas espresso machines, gas dryers or flame burners. The latter are also used in bigger size for gardening, supplying high temperature airflows very fast and efficient. Furthermore, some households have saunas being equipped with natural gas heaters or use gas dryers.

Principally **air conditioning (cooling)** can be performed by gas applications. However, although there are companies offering these technologies for households (and other sectors),¹⁹ these applications are

¹⁹ Zukunft ERDGAS 2019.

not commonly used.²⁰ Theoretically, adsorption chillers and absorption chillers can be used for providing cooling. For **process cooling**, there is no technology known to the authors so far, which households use, to produce process cold from gas.

Electricity is most commonly supplied via grid to households. However, there are some technologies, producing heat and electricity simultaneously at household level. These include (micro) CHPs, small gas motors or fuel cells. As small units, these technologies are also summed up as “electricity producing heaters”.²¹ For **mechanical energy** supply no common technology is known to the authors.

2.1.2 Substitution technologies

For mechanical energy, lighting or cooling and process heat, electricity-based technologies are state of the art in households. Concerning process heat, especially modern induction stoves and fast starting ovens present equivalent replacements. Thus, key integration or substitution technologies focus on heating space heating and warmwater (resp. low temperature provision). Modern and innovative concepts include electrical heat pumps, electrical floor heating, heating rods, flow heaters and electric boilers. With exception of the radiant panel heating, these technologies produce hot water as well as space heating. The following introduces the most important substitution technologies.

Heating rods are easiest to install and offer a large scope of installation capacities of 2-1,000 kW. In combination with a buffer storage, they provide both hot water and space heating. The high density of the tubular heating element provides a very good insulation resistance and a high degree of ohmic resistance.²² In contrast, **flow heaters** do not require a storage system. They may be integrated in hot water cycles or heating systems directly. Flow heaters consist of a pressure tank with an inlet pipe, an outlet pipe and an electrical connector housing. The electrical circuits are positioned inside the flow pipe. Because of the high electrical resistance, the heating elements heat up. Water flows along the heating elements through the pipe and absorbs the thermal energy. The efficiency is similarly high to that of heating rods (around 99 %).²³ Possible installation vary between 2 kW to 5 MW.

Electrical floor heating provides a constant heat yield which serves to heat up rooms. The temperature is perceived to be 1-2 °C warmer. This effect leads to a reduction in energy demand of around 10 % without incurring losses of comfort.²⁴ The floor storage heating system transforms electricity to heat and emits it with an intentional delay to the ground level of the floor. The heating capacity of systems lies between 70 - 90 W/m².²⁵

Heat pumps offer efficient supply of environmental heat by vaporising and electrically condensing a refrigerant and therefore increasing its temperature. The refrigerant is then cooled, liquefied and then vaporised again in a continuous cycle. The preliminary temperature can be sourced via different mediums. Principle possible implementations are air/water, brine/water or water/water. These mediums deliver their temperature by means of pipes which function as probes. The advantage of heat pumps lies in the high conversion factor that is applied by using existing source temperatures and raising these to a higher level. The invested electrical energy transforms to thermal energy by a factor (coefficient of performance – COP) of 2.5 to 5 depending on the installation.²⁶ It should also be noted that the real COP differs from the laboratory measurement and that a lower annual COP can be expected over the

²⁰ In AGEB 2018, no gas usage is reported for cooling (see p. 26).

²¹ See: Fuchs 2017, p. 102.

²² VDE 2015, pp. 32–34.

²³ VDE 2015, 35-36.

²⁴ VDE 2015, p. 37.

²⁵ VDE 2015, pp. 37–38.

²⁶ Fh IWES and Fh IBP 2017, COP depends on surrounding temperature.

whole year.²⁷ With regard to the heat source 60–80 % of the energy is obtained from the environment. This characteristic enables heat pumps to deliver thermal energy far more efficiently compared to other heating technologies. Further substitution technologies include non-typical sector coupling technologies like **solar heating** or usage of **biomass**, which only might be included into the definition of sector coupling technologies on a very broad perspective.²⁸

Apart from single household solutions, district heating offers considerable potential for drawing heat from various technologies. These include heat pumps as well as power-to-heat, using big size boilers to heat up water. Within this analysis, district heating is seen as tool, allowing to transport heat to the final consumers. Thus, it is not included in the analysis focussing on the final consumption.

2.2 Trade and Services

Next to office-related businesses, where gas is mostly used for space heating, e.g. restaurants and hotels or manufacturing enterprises need process heat up to high temperature levels.²⁹ With close to 130 TWh final energy consumption from natural gas, the share of natural gas is around 50 % of the total, non-electric, final energy demand.³⁰ Furthermore, heat supply accounts over 85 % of the non-electric final energy consumption and 99 % of the final energy consumption from natural gas. Space heating again is the dominating field of application for natural gas, being responsible for 108 TWh in 2017 (thus, 85 % of the natural gas consumption).³¹ The sector can be divided into 13 different sub-sectors.³² Though, above 85 % of the whole gas consumption in trade and services occurs within four subsectors.³³ These are “office-related enterprises”, “trade”, “hospitals, schools, swimming pools” and the “catering branch” as can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Total final energy consumption of gas for each sub-sector of trade and services from 2013 until 2017

Source: Data from Schlomann et al. (2015a, pp. 53–56) in combination with Geiger et al. (2018, pp. 35–40), values are scaled to mean of AGEB and IfE

²⁷ Brischke et al. 2012, p. 10.

²⁸ Wietschel et al. 2018, p. 6.

²⁹ Geiger 2016.

³⁰ Geiger et al. 2018, p. 35.

³¹ Geiger et al. 2018, p. 52.

³² See: Schlomann et al. 2015b, p. 5.

³³ Schlomann et al. 2015a; Geiger et al. 2018.

2.2.1 Recent Technologies

There exist several coincidences between the household and the trade and service sector concerning recent gas technologies. However, some specialities do exist in this sector, which are highlighted in the following.

For **lighting** gas is not relevant.³⁴ However, some applications do exist e.g. gas fireplaces can be found in some hotels and spas or patio heaters supply light and heat at restaurants, both combining heat and light. Further, the same technologies as in the household sector can be found (see: 2.1.1). This also applies to **space heating** technologies. As the demand regularly exceeds that of a household, larger production units are more common. Technologically, there are no differences to condensing boilers or gas-fired boilers for the household sector.³⁵ One speciality is the increasing existence of CHP units compared to the household sector. These are mainly found in hospitals, office buildings, schools and spas³⁶. Further, mobile heat production units can be found in form of patio heaters in the hotel and restaurant sector, as well as radiant heaters for terraces.³⁷ In addition, waste heat of some production processes can be used (e.g. in laundries),³⁸ which represents an indirect use of gas for space heating.

In contrast to households, several branches in the trade and service sector have specific requirements regarding **process heat**. While offices and small businesses in general have only little need for process heat, hotels and restaurants need process heat. For small and medium sized restaurants used devices include gas ovens or stoves, while bigger restaurants or catering companies may use barbecues, bain-maries, steamer, rack-type dishwasher or even pasta cookers. From the top four natural gas consuming sub-sectors, especially in hospitals, a lot of process heat is consumed. For example, autoclaves in (central) sterilization or disinfection facilities require process heat e.g. for the cleaning of medical instruments. Further, hospitals use gas in laundries or for heating of indoor pools, as spas do, too.³⁹ Other usages include heating of saunas in spas. Additionally, gas burners are applied in several production processes, e.g. in the manufacturing and building sector. Applications are for example flame burners or welding machines. Other applications are gas fired ovens for metal processing in locksmith's, engineering and welding shops for the manufacturing of metal products.⁴⁰ This includes technologies like curing ovens, oxidation furnaces, melting ovens or sinter ovens.⁴¹ Many (other) processes need (pressurized) hot steam. Examples of technologies used are steam generators, steam boilers and tunnel finishers in the textile and laundry industry or scalding and depilating machines for butchers. Moreover, high temperature heat is used in bakeries in continuous ovens, backing ovens or trolley ovens. Finally, smoke and heat are used in (hot) smoking plants from the fishing industry and by butchers.⁴²

Air conditioning (cooling) includes central air conditioning as well as mobile systems or decentral split air conditioning units.⁴³ The dissemination of air conditioning (cooling) technologies is significantly higher in the trade and service sector than in the household sector. While most air conditioning appli-

³⁴ Schlomann et al. 2015a, p. 121.

³⁵ See technology description in BDEW 2016.

³⁶ Schlomann et al. 2015a, p. 134.

³⁷ For a broad overview of technologies see: BDEW 2019.

³⁸ Schlomann et al. 2015a, pp. 133–134.

³⁹ Schlomann et al. 2015a, p. 162.

⁴⁰ Kornhardt 2009, p. 13.

⁴¹ Gewerbegas 2013.

⁴² Schlomann et al. 2015a, p. 179.

⁴³ Schlomann et al. 2015a, p. 126.

cations use electricity, some hospitals use absorption and adsorption chillers to cool down their building. Therefore, heat from gas fired, decentral CHPs is used, which is not needed during the summer.⁴⁴ Other possibilities are gas fired heat pumps (also for cooling)⁴⁵.

Process cooling is needed especially in the food industry, but like air conditioning predominant supplied by electricity. **Electricity** production using gas on site is a common technology in the trade and services sector. This includes gas motors, (micro) turbines or fuel cells, mostly using cogeneration. Like electricity, **mechanical energy** can be provided by turbines and motors, both allowing for flexible and fast changes in production. In addition to that, indirect usage of gas includes the production of pressurized air by compressors, which can be found in manufacturing processes or by car shops. An additional application of gas for providing mechanical energy are forklift trucks.⁴⁶

2.2.2 Substitution technologies

In the trade and service sector similar substitution technologies can be applied as in the household sector (see 2.1.2). The bulk of natural gas is used to supply space heating and hot water. Thus, especially **heat pumps** are a reasonable alternative to conventional heating technologies. This includes even low temperature processes heat, as state of the art heat pumps can reach installations of multiple megawatts and temperatures over 90 °C.⁴⁷ There are multiple options for heat sources, e.g. server exhaust heat, waste heat from cooling processes, geothermal energy, solar heat or exhaust air. Further, **resistance heater** and **electrode hot water boiler** can be applied, where hot water or even steam is desired. However, high temperature processes are difficult to supply by substitution technologies.

2.3 Industry

The total final energy consumption of the industrial sector in Germany reached 740 TWh in 2017 which equals to 29 % of the total final German energy consumption.⁴⁸ In 2017 the German industry made up about 35 % of the German natural gas demand, with gas being the most important source of energy.⁴⁹ A large part of gas usage in production processes comes from high and middle temperature process heat.⁵⁰ In addition to that, natural gas is an important basis of the chemical industry with a share of 11 % of used resources.⁵¹ Because of the heterogeneity of industrial production, it makes sense to reduce the analysis of the status quo of gas usage to the top five industrial branches (which sum up to close to 65 % of the natural gas usage in the industry sector in 2017).⁵² These are:

- Basic chemicals industry
- Food and tobacco production
- Production of pulp, paper and paper products
- Metal production
- Glass and ceramic production.

Due to the heterogeneous energy demand especially for heat, it is reasonable to have a closer look at the demand structure. Table 1 gives an overview of the heat demand and supplied by natural gas in the most important industries.

⁴⁴ For example see: UKE 2015. Allows to enhance the full load hours of CHPs.

⁴⁵ Märtel n.d.

⁴⁶ Gewerbegas 2013.

⁴⁷ Wolf et al. 2014, p. 114.

⁴⁸ AGEb 2019b, 11; 30.

⁴⁹ AGEb 2019b, p. 13.

⁵⁰ Fraunhofer-Institut für System- und Innovationsforschung 2016.

⁵¹ VCI - Verband der Chemischen Industrie e.V., „Daten-Fakten-Rohstoffbasis-der-chemischen-Industrie“, 1.

⁵² Fh ISI 2019, p. 83.

Table 1: Structure of finale energy consumption from natural gas for heat production for selected industrial branches

Branch of industry	Hot water and space heating	Process heat				Total	Share of gas based heat demand
		<100°C	100 - 500°C	500 - 1000°C	>1000°C		
Basic chemicals industry*	2.50	29.96	46.59	99.49	24.51	203.00	25 %
Food and Tobacco**	13.40	46.04	56.57	-	-	116.00	14 %
Pulp and Paper	2.00	16.80	61.90	-	-	80.70	10 %
Metal production*	0.30	0.33	1.04	12.29	48.22	62.20	8 %
Glass and ceramic*	2.20	0.83	1.28	19.11	39.57	63.00	8 %
Total	20.40	93.95	167.38	130.90	112.30	524.9	65 %

Data without unit in PJ/a

Source: Data from Fh ISI (2019, p. 83) process heat scaled based on Nast et al. (2010, p. 6).

*Scaled based on superordinate industry sector.

As can be seen, the basic chemical industry demands a significant share of process heat in the area of 500 °C – 1,000 °C (approx. 50 %), while the glass and ceramic industry as well as metal production demand high share of heat even above 1,000 °C (78 % resp. 65 %). However, over all five branches, the dominant consumption appears between 100 °C - 500 °C (circa 33 %). Space heating is relatively insignificant compared to process heating with less than 5 % of the heating demand.

2.3.1 Recent Technologies

Lighting, space heating and air conditioning (cooling) are not analyzed, as similar technologies as described above can be expected. **Process cold** is especially relevant in the food production industry. However, natural gas-fuelled applications are rarely found. Indirect applications are industrial CHP-plants, which are supplemented with absorption chillers to increase full load hours or flexibility.⁵³ Further, some indirect applications can be found in the chemical industry where waste heat is used with absorption chillers for cooling. **Mechanical energy** is also rarely supplied by natural gas. Many processes are already electrified (e.g. pumps, valves) and some may be electrified soon, like forklifts. However, in the energy intensive industry, some natural gas fuel compressors exist. Furthermore, natural gas is used for gas motors.

Process heat is the most important final energy use for the industry sector as discussed before. The biggest share of natural gas is used in the *basic chemical industry*. Here it is particularly used for steam production. Furthermore, natural gas is used in steam-cracking-processes (e.g. fertilizer production) as well as for exhaust gas cleaning (e.g. NO_x-reduction by applying thermal reduction processes at temperatures above 1,000 °C).⁵⁴ Thus, both high temperature steam as well as gas-air mixtures are produced. Where useful, natural gas is burned in CHPs to produce steam (heat) and power. However, this is limited to processes, where a relative high amount of power is needed next to process heat.

Very homogeneous production routes can be found in the *paper industry*. Next to huge energy demands for the pulp production where natural gas only plays a minor role for heat supply, in boiling processes as well as thickening and burning of black liquor in recovery boilers, natural gas is applied for steam production used for the drying process of paper machines.⁵⁵ Hence, steam at moderate temperatures (drying) as well as high temperature heat (thermal recycling) are needed.

The *food production industry* is very heterogeneous, compared to the paper industry. However, some similar processes can be identified. This includes pasteurising including ultra-high temperature (UHT)

⁵³ Heinrich et al. 2014, pp. 70–82.

⁵⁴ Fleiter 2013, p. 129.

⁵⁵ Fleiter 2013, p. 551 ff; Umweltbundesamt (UBA) 2014.

treatments up to 150 °C (e.g. milk or other perishable products). Thereby two options exist – direct heating of the product or a steam treatment (e.g. fish conservation). Further applications include the preservation of products in smokers, energy intensive drying processes (e.g. starches and starch production), cooking process to reduce liquid portion (e.g. sugar industry) or frying and baking processes in the bakery industry.⁵⁶

In the *metal industry*, natural gas is used to produce direct reduced iron (DRI, Midrex-Process) for steel production.⁵⁷ Furthermore, it is used for producing heat in furnaces (e.g. ladle furnaces or heat injection in blast furnaces) to perform the subsequent secondary metallographic treatment. Additionally, it is applied as fuel in rotary kilns to produce quicklime or in rosters and flame ovens.⁵⁸

Finally, the *glass and ceramics industry* uses a lot of natural gas within its production processes. However, two processes are responsible for most of the energy demand. This is melting of glass on the one hand and baking of ceramics on the other hand. For the first process, nearly exclusively natural gas is burned to reach the temperature of the glass needed. Further processes within the glass industry are melting including stress-relief annealing or refining processes. Generally, this secondary energy demand could be satisfied by electricity as well. However, due to low natural gas prices, a fuel switch is not economical. Thus, applications of natural gas can also be found in the brick, lime or gypsum production, where natural gas is used to heat up furnaces at low costs to high temperatures. An overview of temperature needs for selected processes of the energy intensive industries is given in Figure 3.

Electricity production by natural gas-fired CHP-plants is a common technology in the industry sector, especially due to economic advantages because of the need of heat and power in many production processes. Among the industry branches, CHP usage is especially common within the strongly integrated chemical industry as well as the metal and the paper industries.⁵⁹ Next to normal (combined cycle) CHP-plants, the first fuel cell-based plant above one megawatt was installed in 2016.⁶⁰

Figure 3: Process heat demand of selected processes in the industry
Source: Data from (Frisch et al. 2013, p. 13)

2.3.2 Key integration technologies

Processes that rely on the chemical compounds of natural gas or need too high temperatures for electrification, can only be defossilized by synthetic gas. However, several processes can be substituted by

⁵⁶ Fleiter 2013, p. 513 ff.

⁵⁷ Solomon 2007, p. 460.

⁵⁸ Fleiter 2013, pp. 321–326.

⁵⁹ Statistisches Bundesamt 9/28/2017.

⁶⁰ VDE Verband der Elektrotechnik Elektronik Informationstechnik e. V. 2016.

applying different technologies. Nevertheless, in most cases a change in the process chain is needed, which implies high costs and in general the need of major revisions. The following will give insights regarding a range of electric-based industrial operations for possible substitutions.

For **process heat by steam or hot water**, electrical AC-boilers can be used. They heat up water by using the resistance of the water itself. Maximum temperatures of boilers are around 240 °C with a maximum pressure of 30 bar. Installed capacities vary from 1 to 120 MW. This can be especially useful, if district heating is applied in an industry park, as there exists already systems applying this technology.⁶¹

Furthermore, **induction heating** can be applied. Induction heating is based on generating changing eddy currents in a conductive object. This is achieved by placing an alternating current carrying coil around or next to the material and using this coil to induce eddy currents in the object. Direct induction heating is used for “heating directly, heat treating or melting conductive materials”⁶², while indirect heating is used for melting nonconductive materials like plastics. To do so, first a conductive material is heated, which heats up the nonconductive material. So, inductive heating can be used for “hardening, tempering, annealing, normalizing and stress relieving”⁶³ of conductive material, or melting material for casting. Induction heating achieves high power densities as well as high heating rates.⁶⁴

Electric arc furnaces are used to melt steel or iron scrap. The metal is melted by a direct electric arc struck from the electrode. The method is not applicable for primary steel production. However, the production of one ton of steel in an electric arc furnace requires approximately 450 kWh, which is about one third to one tenth of the energy demand for one tonne of steel via the primary route (applying oxygen furnaces or integrated blast furnaces). Furthermore, electric arc furnaces are less capital intensive than integrated blast furnaces but due to using electricity having higher operation costs.⁶⁵

Electron beam processing is the principle of converting kinetic energy of an accelerated stream of electrons to heat when hitting the surface of metal. The technology has been around since the beginning of the 20th century.⁶⁶ It is regarded as relatively easy to handle in operation and well controllable. Electron beam heating can heat metal to intense temperatures within very short times. In a high energy vacuum, it can be used as melting technique in order to prevent contamination. Electron beam heating is used in many state-of-the-art production facilities for welding, especially in the automotive industry. It is primarily used as an application for local surface hardening of high-wear components. Another potential application is the curing of multiple layers of web material simultaneously, as well as curing surface coatings.⁶⁷ Electron beam processing is also used for creating crosslinking, radical and graft polymerization reactions in polymers, as well as in exhaust gas processing, and semiconductor device application. Some non-thermal applications include food irradiation and the application of sterilization of medical equipment.⁶⁸

Electric infrared processing is an indirect heating process, in which the energy is conveyed to the work-piece by electromagnetic radiation of heating elements. An electrical current is passed through a solid resistor, which heats up to a desired source temperature to emit infrared radiant energy. “Electric infrared heating systems are generally used where precise temperature control is required to heat

⁶¹ Biedermann and Kolb 2014, p. 51.

⁶² Vairamohan 2014, p. 9.

⁶³ Vairamohan 2014, p. 19.

⁶⁴ Vairamohan 2014, p. 9.

⁶⁵ U.S. Department of Energy 2015, p. 26

⁶⁶ Kashiwagi and Hoshi 2012, p. 48.

⁶⁷ U.S. Department of Energy 2015, p. 29.

⁶⁸ Kashiwagi and Hoshi 2012, pp. 51–52.

treat surfaces, cure coatings, and dry materials, but infrared can also be used in bulk heating applications such as booster ovens.”⁶⁹ Because of the capacity to heat and dry objects within seconds, accurate control is needed. Electric infrared heating is especially used for flat products that are heat treated, dried, or cured.⁷⁰ Short-wave radiators can reach surface temperatures of about 2,000-3,000 K. The overall efficiency of infrared heating is around 50 %. Exemplary applications are the drying and polymerizing of paints and varnishes, heating of thermoplastics, drying of textiles, paper, ceramics or plastics and the hardening of adhesives.⁷¹

Lastly, synthetic gas must be applied, where no other option exists. The **power-to-gas** technology plays a special roll, allowing the production of synthetic gas and replacing natural gas without any changes in the production process. The process is based on electrolysis and subsequent methanation, if needed. Recent developments raise hope that the processes can efficiently support a carbon-neutral energy economy. A study on pilot plants in Germany shows that the technological development is on average as fast or even slightly faster than expected for power-to-methane (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Projections of efficiency of power-to-gas from the literature and values from recent projects
Source: Milanzi (2018a)

Apart from high temperature process heat, many different technologies, which are apt to substitute natural gas in households and businesses in trade and services, also apply in the industry sector. First and foremost, **process heat pumps** have the potential to cover 23 % of the German industrial heat demand.⁷² Especially sectors like the food, paper and chemistry industry offer large potentials for applications above 80 °C to 150 °C. Particularly with drying, evaporating, cooking, washing and cleaning, the thermal discharge itself can be used as the heat source. Also, in the metal-working industry many processes work beneath 100 °C. This makes them viable for state-of-the-art process heat pump technology. Process heat pumps that can supply temperatures exceeding 140 °C are currently being developed. Different companies are experimenting with condensation temperatures of 110 to 170 °C.⁷³

⁶⁹ U.S. Department of Energy 2015, p. 9.

⁷⁰ U.S. Department of Energy 2015, pp. 27–28.

⁷¹ VDE 2015, p. 64.

⁷² Wolf et al. 2014, p. 125.

⁷³ Wolf et al. 2014, p. 32.

3 Analysis

The substitution of natural gas is a need if no carbon capture technology is used as stated above. After the presentation of the status quo and possible technological solutions to do so (chapter 2), the following describes the methodology for an analysis of the potential of substitution technologies. The methodology is split into two parts. While first of all, a meta-analysis is done to identify the most promising technologies for substitution (section 3.1 results in section 4.1), second, a model based analysis is performed, to identify possible substitution pathways from an economic, cost-minimizing perspective (section 3.2 results in section 4.2). As most of the natural gas is consumed in the heating sector (see chapter 2), the analysis focusses on it. Furthermore, a focus is on technologies already accessible and which can be fast introduced or more widely used by end consumers as stated above.

3.1 Meta-analysis

To identify the most promising technologies for substituting gas-based technologies, a meta-analysis is performed. Therefore, current studies (not older than five years) are analysed, which on the one hand focus on sector coupling and on the other describe this sector integration for the heat sector to a sufficient extent. Furthermore, studies focusing on one demand sector (households, services or industry) are ignored. As a regional focus, Germany is chosen, since the later analysis concentrates on this area. All in all, more than 40 studies are analysed, and 20 studies are identified as being relevant.

To measure the expected relevance of possible substitution technologies from the literature analysis, the following approach is chosen. First, it is expected, that if an author assumes the technology being important, the technology will be included, thus mentioned, in the individual study. Furthermore, it is assumed, that the quantity of denominations correlates positive to the significance an author expects for this technology. Thus, the relevant studies are checked for possible substitution technologies and the relevance of these technologies is measured by the quantity of denomination in different studies as well as within these studies. Finally, a list of relevant technologies is found, which are analysed more in depth with a quantitative model as described in the following.

3.2 Model and scenarios

The model for analysing transition and substitution pathways of natural gas final energy consumption represents a system where every year additional conventional (natural gas based) heating must be replaced by substitution technologies until a carbon free heat supply is reached in 2050. The model incorporates economic competition between selected substitution technologies (within the range of possibility heat supply per technology) and calculates cost-minimized transition paths. Inputs to the model include annual heat demand to be replaced in each sector (households, industry, trade and services), technology parameters and technology specific learning curves that represent investment costs as a function of the cumulatively built capacity. Four different scenarios are analysed, that differ in the rate at which natural gas based heat supply must be substituted ("Prompt" or "Acting Late") as well as the inclusion of high-temperature heat supply in the industry sector (with or without). Figure 5 shows the overall structure of the model.

As can be seen in the study "Climate Change Scenario 2050"⁷⁴ of the BMU, a 80 % THG-reduction scenario still allows some natural gas based emissions for high temperature heat applications in the industry (HTI), while there are no emissions from natural gas left under the 95 % Scenario. Following these findings, two substitution scenarios are developed, one assuming a full replacement of natural gas until 2050 (corresponding to 95 %, thus with HTI replacement) and one scenario not replacing HTI. Without CCS, both correspondence to equivalent replacement of natural gas consumption.

⁷⁴ Öko-Institut and Fh ISI 2015, p. 33.

Inputs	Algorithm	Results
Demand:	For every year until 2050:	Technical
- Annual heat demand to be covered separated in: 1) general heat demand, 2) low and 3) high temperature heat demand	Cost minimization:	- Expansion of integration technologies over time
Technologies:	1) Check for energy demand	- Installed capacities (per year and absolute)
- Efficiencies, full load hours, costs, maximal potentials and minimal expansion rate	2) Build minimum capacity per technology	- Supplied heat per technology
- Learning curves	3) Build cheapest additional technology mix based on annuities	
Scenarios (2x2):	After minimization :	Economical
- Acting late or prompt	4) Update costs via learning curves	- Costs per Scenario
- With HTI (95 % THG reduction) or without demand (80 % THG reduction)	5) Restart	

Figure 5: Structure of quantitative analysis

Source: by author

Assuming that energy efficiency will reduce heat demand by 20 % until 2050 (hence, 125 TWh), approximately 500 TWh of natural gas-based heat demand need to be substituted in 2050 under the 95% scenario assumptions.⁷⁵ Hence, in the model, substitution is driven by predefined amount of heat to be substituted each year and not by CO₂ emission limits. Furthermore, it is assumed that approximately half of the industry heat demand is above 200 °C (55 %).⁷⁶ This is defined as high-temperature industrial heat demand (HTI) and possible replacement pathways are included in two of the four scenarios (see Figure 5). For every scenario, a specific substitution pathway is assumed. These pathways correspond to heat demand that needs to be satisfied by heat production from (new) integration technologies. While in the S1 and S2 scenarios a residual share of natural gas remains for HTI, reflecting the 80 % reduction BMU scenario, in the S3 and S4 scenarios, reflecting 95 % reduction, this share is replaced as well. Furthermore, two different natural gas replacement pathways are defined differing in the speed of replacing natural gas-based heat supply by integration technologies: “Acting late” (S2 and S4) assuming an exponential replacement and acting “Prompt”, where replacement follows a logarithmic course. Although both pathways aim for the same result in 2050, one has to consider, that the amount of CO₂-emissions are a lot less in the “Prompt” scenarios compared to the “Acting late” scenarios (approximately twice as high).

For cost comparison, a business-as-usual scenario was modelled, where it was possible to invest in gas condensing boilers to satisfy heat demand to be substituted. In order to account for resulting CO₂ emissions from an economical perspective, natural gas got a CO₂ cost component with a price of 5.8 €/tCO₂ in 2017 geometrically increasing to 350 €/tCO₂ in 2050. Regardless of that CO₂ price, it turned out that in the model well-developed low-cost gas condensing boilers are the dominating technology even until 2050. Hence, we conclude that without a fast and effective CO₂ price or regulatory interception in the market, substitution technologies are not able to economically compete outside research laboratories but exclude this from further analyses.

The applied model is formulated as an optimization model, minimizing overall system costs on an annual basis. System costs are represented by fixed investment costs and annual variable costs (maintenance, servicing and energy costs) that are converted to annuities to account for the different lifetimes of technologies. Furthermore, investment costs are assumed to decrease with the installed capacity along a given technology specific learning curve. The mathematical formulation is now presented.

⁷⁵ Rogler 2018, p. 43.

⁷⁶ Fh IWES and Fh IBP 2017, p. 31 Assuming, that coal is primary used in the steel production, the overall sum of energy carriers overestimates the temperature level for natural gas applications.

For each year $t \in T$, in this case $T = \{2017, \dots, 2050\}$, a linear minimization problem determines the capacity $x_{s,t}$ of technology s to be installed in year t such that the production costs are minimized. The objective function is expressed by

$$\min z_t = \sum_{s \in S} x_{s,t} \cdot \left(C_{inv,s,t}(X_{s,t-1}) + \sum_{\tau=0}^{l_s} \frac{h_s \cdot C_{energy,s,(t+\tau)} \cdot \eta_s^{-1} + C_{inv,s,t}(X_{s,t-1}) \cdot om_s}{(1+i)^\tau} \right) \cdot \frac{(1+i)^{l_s} \cdot i}{(1+i)^{l_s} - 1}$$

with the constants (where every technology s is from a given set S of substitution technologies)

l_s lifetime in years of technology s

h_s annual full load hours of technology s

η_s efficiency [kW_{th}/kW_{el}] of technology s

om_s percentual annual operation and maintenance costs [% of investment] of technology s

i annual interest rate

$C_{energy,s,t}$ energy costs [€/kW_{el}h] of technology s in year t

$C_{inv,s,t}(\cdot)$ specific investment [€/kW_{th}] as a function of the cumulative absolute installed capacity of technology s in year t

$X_{s,t-1}$ cumulated absolute installed capacities [kW_{th}] of technology s before year t

and the variables

$x_{s,t}$ capacity [kW_{th}] of technology s to be installed in year t

$X_{s,t}$ cumulated absolute installed capacity [kW_{th}] of technology s at the end of year t .

The linear program has the following constraints. Firstly, the cumulated absolute installed capacity $X_{s,t}$ of technology s at the end of year t is given by

$$X_{s,t} = X_{s,t-1} + x_{s,t}$$

Secondly, every substitution technology s has an absolute extension limit $X_{MAX,s}$, due to maximal potentials within the supposed system.

$$X_{s,t} \leq X_{MAX,s}$$

Thirdly, due to production restrictions, the capacity to be installed is upper bounded. Moreover, a (positive) lower bound on the minimum invest is reasonable to assume because of research projects etc. For every substitution technology s and every year t , this yields a constraint of the form:

$$x_{MIN,s,t} \leq x_{s,t} \leq x_{MAX,s,t}$$

The last set of constraints guarantees that the needed heat is provided. To do so, the set of substitution technologies belonging to type j of heat⁷⁷ is denoted by S_j and the needed heat of type j in year t is denoted by $Q_{j,t}$. Then, for each type j of heat and each year t , there exists the constraint

$$Q_{j,t} = \sum_{s \in S_j} X_{s,t} \cdot h_s$$

⁷⁷ See above, for 1) general heat demand by households, trade and services, 2) low and 3) high process heat demand from the industry

4 Findings

The following shows first the results of the meta-analysis. Based on this, the model-based comparison is described, focussing on the most relevant technologies.

4.1 Results of the meta-analysis

The meta-analysis shows, that the most dominating technology are heat pumps in their different forms of configuration (air-water, brine-water or water-water heat pumps). This is reflected in the number of hits per study (see Figure 6) as well as in the number of studies including the technology (see Table 2). Concerning hits per study, power-to-heat in general follows on second rank, with already significantly less hits. Again approximately 50 % less hits are found for power-to-gas and solar thermal energy provision. However, concerning the number of studies naming a technology, solar thermal energy is ranked second, closely followed by power-to-heat, power-to-gas and (deep) geothermal.

Table 2: Meta-analysis - Number of studies including technology

Technology	Studies including Technology	Technology	Studies including Technology
Heat pump	20	Geothermal	16
Solar thermal	19	Electrode boiler	13
Power-to-Heat	18	Heating rods	12
Power-to-Gas	17		

Source: By author, based on (BCG and Prognos AG 2018; Brauner 2019; dena and geea 2017; E4Tech and Fh IEE 2018; enervis 2017; Fh ISE 2015; Prognos et al. 2018; Fh IWES and Fh IBP 2015, 2017; Guminski 2017:33:40; Anne Hagemeyer and Christine Settgest 2019; Philipp Jahnke 9/6/2018; MVV 2018; Öko-Institut et al. 2017; Öko-Institut and Fh ISI 2015; Technische Universität Graz 2018; UBA 2019; VDE 2015; Welsch and Julia 2018; Fh IWES 2015)

Figure 6: Meta-Analysis - Number of hits

Source: By author, based on (BCG and Prognos AG 2018; Brauner 2019; dena and geea 2017; E4Tech and Fh IEE 2018; enervis 2017; Fh ISE 2015; Prognos et al. 2018; Fh IWES and Fh IBP 2015, 2017; Guminski 2017:33:40; Anne Hagemeyer and Christine Settgest 2019; Philipp Jahnke 9/6/2018; MVV 2018; Öko-Institut et al. 2017; Öko-Institut and Fh ISI 2015; Technische Universität Graz 2018; UBA 2019; VDE 2015; Welsch and Julia 2018; Fh IWES 2015)

Resistance heating and electrode hot water boilers seem to be less important, although one must consider that these can be as well subsumed under power-to-heat. Induction heating, radiation heating or flow heating are of less importance if one compares the results of these technologies to the above mentioned (all at least factor five less hits and only low single-digit number of studies mention it at all). Thus, the quantitative analysis focuses on the mentioned technologies. As mentioned above, heat pumps can be split into several different versions. To keep this in mind, three possible heat pumps are

used in the model. These are air-water, brine-water and industrial heat pumps. The latter allows for higher heat temperatures as is presented in the following.

4.2 Model-based comparison of heat supply scenarios

As a result of the meta-analysis, within the model-based analysis, brine-water and air-to-air heat pumps as well as solar thermal energy (as being the most important non-typical sector coupling technology) are assumed to be only used in households. On the other side, industrial heat pumps and electrode boilers (low temperature) and power-to-methane (high temperature) are used to supply industrial heat. Deep geothermal heat, however, can be applied to supply low temperature heat for industry and households.

These technologies are placed in competition with each other in the model under the aforementioned restrictions (see section 3.2). However, due to the restrictions of the analysis concerning the industry sector, HTI is only replaced by power-to-methane as it allows producing synthetic gas and thus, indirectly substituting the natural gas. Moreover, it is assumed that the synthetic methane can be used without investing into additional infrastructure. Further, assumptions for electricity prices are made, considering the current situation of taxes, charges and levies. Therefore, a meta-analysis of the Agentur für Erneuerbare Energien (AEE) for electricity prices until 2050 is used⁷⁸ and two scenarios each for electricity prices for industry customers (for low and high temperature heat) and heat pump tariffs (for other electric driven substitution technologies) are calculated. Furthermore, costs for operation, maintenance and repair works (O&M) are stated as an annual proportional amount of the investment costs. The following parameters are applied for the analysis:

Table 3: Parameter assumptions for quantitative analysis

	Unit	Brine-water heat pump	Air-to-air heat pump	Industrial heat pump	(Deep) Geothermal	Solarthermics	Electrode boiler	Power-to-methane ⁷⁹	Condensation boiler
full load hours	h	1,950	2,340	3,500	3,260	560	3,260	6,000	3,260
efficiency	-	3.9	3.1	4.2	1.0	1.0	0.99	0.64	0.99
installed capacity	GW _{th}	3.422	4.484	0.055	0.337	13.4	0.350	0.0098	7.5
investment costs	€/kW _{th}	1,900	1,650	410	2,910	985	238	1,900	200
O&M costs	%	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.65	1.3	2	5	2
learning factor	-	0.85	0.85	0.80	0.95	0.82	0.95	0.87	0.95
lifetime	a	20	20	15	40	30	15	30	15
min./max. annual expansion rate ⁸⁰	GW _{th}	0.15/4	0.15/4	0.2/2	0.25/0.5	0.5/10	0.2/5	0/	0/
potential ⁸¹	GW	150		13.5	6.8	143.85		13	

Source: Rogler (2018, p. 44), O&M costs from Erlach et al. (2019, pp. 35–37), for electrode assumed same as for condensation boiler, industrial heat pump same as for other heat pumps, Power-to-methane from Schmidt et al. (2018, p. 37), plus assumptions for condensing boilers by author

⁷⁸ AEE, p. 2 gives a range of 50€-100€/MWh for wholesale prices in 2050.

⁷⁹ Installed capacity in GW_{el}, investment costs in €/kW_{gas}, and assuming 1 kW_{gas}h is converted to 1kW_{th}h.

⁸⁰ Max. rate increases geometrically 2 % each year (plus reinvest capacities) while min. rate decreases 10 % each year.

⁸¹ Middle of range except for heat pumps and electrode boilers which are based on assumption by authors. It was found, that under given potential restrictions for Power-to-methane and it is not possible to substitute the high temperature heat needed for the 95 % reduction BMU scenario. Hence, unlimited potential for Power-to-methane was assumed.

4.2.1 S1 – Without HTI “Prompt”

The heat supply in households in scenario S1 is dominated by air-to-air-heat pumps (see *Figure 7*). While solar thermal capacity reaches its maximum technical potential in 2029, it's not able to provide large amounts of heat due to low annual full load hours. In contrast to that, with a cumulative installed capacity of 101 GW_{th} in 2050, air-to-air heat pumps supply around 75 % of heat residential heat supply. Apart from that, brine-water heat pumps and deep geothermal energy are only expanded to a small extend. The low temperature process heat is mostly provided by a rapid increase of industrial heat pumps. Only after their technical potential is reached, electrode boilers are expanded, reaching an installed capacity nearly 12 GW_{th} and providing 45 % of the low temperature industrial heat supply. Even though specific investment costs of the electrode boiler are much lower than of industrial heat pumps, their high operation costs, especially electricity costs, make them way less feasible even until 2050. *Figure 8* shows the annual installed capacity added. Due to the logarithmic substitution pattern, a high amount of capacity must be installed in the first years, decreasing over time. The increase from 2037 onwards is caused by the dismantling of the facilities built during the start-up period, especially for air-to-air heat pumps. After early installed solar thermal installations reach their end of lifetime at the end of 2046, they are fully reinvested. Hence, even though heat pumps experience a tremendous reduction of investment costs from 1650 $\text{€}_{2016}/\text{kW}_{\text{th}}$ to 720 $\text{€}_{2050}/\text{kW}_{\text{th}}$, solar thermics remain the cheaper technology mainly due to their close to zero operation costs. Apart from that, industrial heat pumps are replaced nearly twice over the modelled investment period, showing their cost competitiveness over time.

Figure 7: Results Scenario S1: New installed capacity per technology in GW_{th} (cumulative, top) and energy generated in $\text{TW}_{\text{th},h}$ (bottom)

Source: By author

Figure 8: Annual results scenario S1: Installations per technology and year in GW_{th}
Source: By author

4.2.2 S2 – Without HTI “Acting late”

In Scenario S2 the late introduction of substitution technologies leads to a very different pathway (see Figure 9). Interestingly, while solar thermic technologies are fully developed in the S1 scenario, they play a minor role here. Due to the low expansion of solar thermics in the early years, the rapid reduction of investment costs for air-to-air heat pumps overcompensates their high operation costs and leads to an overall higher deployment of 135 GW. This shows the tight cost competition between solar thermics and air-to-air heat pumps during the first years. As can be seen Figure 10, another difference is the late deployment of electrode boilers, since industrial heat pumps are able to cover the whole industrial low temperature heat demand until 2040. Apart from that, the substitution pattern over time is relatively similar to that in S1, showing the small solution space, when substituting these large amounts of natural gas-based heat supply. In combination with and in contrast to scenario S1, in S2, no concentrated replacement period can be seen. This is due to the slow increase in capacities and relatively few devices to be replaced within the observation period. However, these installations must be replaced during the 2070s.

Figure 9: Results Scenario S2: New installed capacity per technology in GW_{th} (cumulative, top) and energy generated in $TW_{th,h}$ (bottom)

Source: By author

Figure 10: Annual results scenario S2: Installations per technology and year in GW_{th}
Source: By author

4.2.3 S3 – With HTI “Prompt” and S4 – With HTI “acting late”

Both scenarios S3 and S4 are very equal to the scenarios S1 and S2 when comparing the low temperature heat demand, as space heating, warm water and low-temperature process heat is supplied by similar technologies. Furthermore, power-to-gas is applied to fulfil the high temperature heat demand of the industry. As described above, the applied model does not allow for a broader differentiation in the industry sector. Thus, power-to-gas is the only technology surely allowing to replace this demand. In S3 like in S1, one can see a first replacement in the 2030s, when electrode boilers are replaced mainly by industrial heat pumps. For S3, again, deep geothermal energy and the brine-water heat pump do not exceed the minimum construction bound. If one compares the build-up paths of scenario S3 and S4, one can see again, that S4 is much flatter. In 2030, the output of the air-source heat pumps and power-to-methane will only reach $7.45 GW_{th}$ and $4.29 GW_{th}$ in scenario S4, respectively, while in scenario S3, $28.5 GW_{th}$ of air-source heat pumps and $16.4 GW_{th}$ power-to-methane plants are projected.

Figure 11: Results Scenario S3 (top) and S4 (bottom): Energy generated in TW_{th}
Source: By author

4.2.4 Comparison of economic effects

The overall system costs are depicted in Table 4. As can be seen, they strongly depend on the substitution pattern, i.e. whether acting prompt or late. Interestingly, acting late seems to be much cheaper than acting prompt. This is mainly based on the following effects: 1) the real discount rate of 6 % makes

it much cheaper to invest capital later (same holds for inflation) and 2) the total amount of heat substituted when acting prompt is much higher than when acting late (around 90 %), which is not taking into account when comparing costs only.

Table 4: Cumulated discounted real costs for 2017–2050 in €₂₀₁₆ (not taking operation costs after 2050 into account)

[Billion Euros]	S1	S2	S3	S4
Lower prices	288	112	426	159
Higher prices	292	115	437	165

Source: By author

In contrast to substitution pattern, the difference in electricity prices does not have a large impact on total cumulated discounted real system costs. This, again, is due to the discount and inflation of costs that appear later in time, i.e. the difference is reduced since payments are made over time. Thus, across scenarios, the difference is rather equal. Nevertheless, the share of electricity costs in total system costs is quite large. This is not surprising, as most of the technologies need electricity for supplying heat. Further, one can argue, that although investment costs are still high, by far the biggest problem for substituting natural gas-based heating are electricity costs, which corresponds to findings in other studies.⁸² Further, one must state, that the CO₂ ambition between the scenarios is not the same. Thus, due to the fast progress in S1 and S3, a lot less CO₂ is produced than in S2, resp. S4. This must be considered, if one compares the results. Thus, if CO₂ costs are included, the scenarios will move closer to each other.

4.3 Critical evaluation and validation

The model shows that a substitution is principally possible within the limits of the model, including upper boundaries for the implementation of several technologies. Further, the heat supplied by heat pumps is within the expected range for reaching a fully decarbonized energy system compared to other studies.⁸³ As is shown above, the method itself is a reasonable approach for analysing the substitution of natural gas applications, especially in the heating sector. However, one must state that there still exist several limits, which give options to further developments. First, the depiction of the industrial sector is still very basic. Hence, the substitution pathways (S3 and S4) are representing the HTI-demand on a very highly aggregated level, but consistent to the low temperature demand. Allowing only power-to-gas for high temperature process heat is reasonable if no detailed information of the heat demand is accessible. However, this leads to a limitation of the model regarding the competition between different technologies in the industry sector since there basically is only one viable option. Further, the results are also limited to the technologies accessible to the model. Although the most important technologies were identified and included in the model, further technologies might be possible and might even prove to be cheaper for special applications. Additionally, the model only differentiates the demand in terms of temperature by now. However, as the model allows limiting the application of different technologies to specific demands, a more detailed structure can be implemented here. Finally, except for solar thermal, no non-electric technology is included. Additional technologies or energy supplies like biogas could change the results in this case, as well as different efficiency estimations for the heating sector. However, concerning biomass, still big uncertainties do exist about the usable amounts, as most other sectors also do consider biomass application.

⁸² Grosse 2019

⁸³ Jülch et al. 2018, p. 15.

5 Conclusion and further research

All in all, the analysis presents several possibilities for replacing natural gas applications in all important demand sectors. As stated in chapter 2, especially the industry sector is demanding, when it comes to a direct electrification. Nevertheless, as argued within chapter 3, power-to-gas is available to fill this gap. This implies that a full transition to a fossil free future until 2050 is possible. However, as stated in section 4.2.4, this leads to comparatively high costs, if one does not include CO₂ costs in a business-as-usual scenario.

From the research perspective the applied methodology seems to be interesting, as it generally leads to useful results. However, ensuing, more detailed implementations of different technologies as well as more demand restriction (thus, a stronger link between the demand and supply option) seem to be interesting. To do so, a matrix of possible technologies and delivered useful energy, not only focussing on temperature but also on the media needed (e.g. hot water or radiation) would be useful and can be developed from a broad literature analysis. Unfortunately, for the industry sector even this approach seems ambiguous, due to the heterogeneity of the sector. Here, several further analyses are needed beforehand to close the gap. Last, the model itself should be linked to a power market model to gain insights into the interaction of the heat and power market. First, this can be implemented by a soft link. However, for later analyses (2040-2050) the interaction between the heat and power sector must be studied more in detail and the demand side management aspects need to be taken into account more specifically.

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